

THE ASSESSMENT OF HOPE, SELF-ESTEEM, POSITIVE OUTLOOK TO ACADEMIC SUCCESS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS: BASIS FOR MENTAL HEALTH INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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The Assessment of Hope, Self-Esteem, Positive Outlook to Academic Success of Senior High School Students: Basis for Mental Health Intervention Program

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Abstract

This study sought to assess the Hope, Self-esteem, and Positive Outlook of the students. This study identified the demographic profile of the respondents; hope; self-esteem; positive outlook; academic success; and the significant correlation of hope, self-esteem, and positive outlook of the respondents. A descriptive correlational research design was used in this study. This method described the hope, self-esteem, positive outlook, and academic achievement of the students and the relationship between them. This study was conducted in nine (9) Public Secondary Schools in Lopez West District. The respondents of the study are Senior High School Students. The researcher utilized the 3 Adult Hope Scale, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, Revised-Life Orientation Test, and the Research Made Questionnaire. The results show that the indicators of hope were mostly true to them; they disagree with the indicators of self-esteem; and agree with the positive outlook. In terms of the academic success of the respondents, they agreed that they acquired the desired skills and competencies and were satisfied with their learning experiences. Moreover, there is a significant relationship between hope and academic success and a positive outlook and academic success. On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between self-esteem and academic success. Therefore, the implementation of the Mental Health Intervention Program is needed to address mental health needs at the same time monitor the academic success of the respondents.

Keywords: *hope, self-esteem, positive outlook, academic success*

Introduction

In December 2019, the World Health Organization declared the COVID 19 pandemic. The whole world is affected. In the Philippines, the lockdowns and quarantine protocols shifted the traditional classes to online and modular modalities. The abrupt transition of the educational system brings effects on the students' academic success due to the isolation and lack of interaction with fellow students and teachers.

The Philippine Star (2021) included that one-fifth of Filipino elementary and high school students, equivalent to more than five million heads, failed to enroll for academic year 2020-2021, and will likely miss enrollment again this coming school year 2021-2022 as pandemic uncertainties continue to plague normal life. For the last two school years, the enrollment and graduation rate in the senior high school has been affected. The decrease in the promotion and graduation rate is caused by the poor academic achievements of the students. Some of the students failed to comply with the academic requirements, drop out, and choose to stop because of different factors and some are caused by the pandemic. The researcher looked at these scenarios and came up with the idea of how the Guidance Coordinator and Mental Health Coordinator can help the students.

Researchers found factors affecting academic achievement and the student's quality performance. They indicated internal factors such as hope, self-esteem, and positive outlook that affect the academic success of the learners.

The study of Cheavens et al. (2005) showed that the hopeful thinking of an individual greatly impacts to their academic success. Students with high hope demonstrate superior academic performance when compared to students with low hopefulness across elementary, junior high school, high school, and college. Hopeful students are more likely to engage in meaningful school activities; they, in turn, are more likely to achieve better academic performance (Amundson et al., 2013).

In addition, the researcher indicated the impact of the self-esteem of the learners on their academic success. As mentioned by Zhao et al., (2021) in their studies, adolescent self-esteem positively predicts academic engagement. Individuals with high levels of self-esteem set stricter standards and only consider themselves "good enough" when they met those standards, resulting in positive self-evaluation and increasing academic engagement (Filippello et al., 2019). Tohid et al., (2014) indicate in their study that there is a very high correlation between academic success and self-esteem and concluded that there is a significant positive correlation.

Moreover, the researcher of this study also explored the correlation between a positive outlook and the academic success of the students. Optimism, within certain ranges, has generally a positive correlation with academic success, and especially with its self-perception. Students who experience better academic achievement in college have more successful careers and experience better life outcomes (Rand et al., 2020). Students who perceive positive expectancies in the pursuit of goals are more likely to persevere in the face of difficulty and identify more ways to reach the goals set in the event of obstacles.

In this study, the researcher determined the level of hope, self-esteem, positive outlook, and academic success of senior high school students during the pandemic. The result aimed to investigate how hope, self-esteem, and a positive outlook affect the students' academic success.

Research Objectives

This study investigated the students' hope, self-esteem, and positive outlook, and managed their academic success as the basis to create an intervention program that will aid the students to strengthen their mental health. Specifically, this study addressed the following:

1. To analyze the students' mental health perspective in terms of:
 - 1.1. hope;
 - 1.2. self-esteem; and
 - 1.3. life orientation.
2. To assess the student's academic success in terms of:
 - 2.1. acquisition of desired skills and competencies; and
 - 2.2. academic satisfaction.
3. To evaluate the significant relationship between the students' mental health perspective, and their academic success and academic achievement.

Literature Review

Hope and Academic Success

Snyder began this work by developing a theoretical model of hope that is based in goal-directed thinking. Hope theory involves a person's ability to conceptualize goals, develop specific strategies or pathways to reach those goals, and initiate and sustain the motivation or agency for using those strategies (Gallagher et al., 2017). Hope is defined as a perceived capability of an individual to derive pathways to desired goals and motivate oneself via agency thinking to use those pathways (Snyder, 2002). It is the ability of a person to create and motivate himself to achieve his goals.

Youth with high hope are differed from students with low hope. Further, youth reporting high hope also differed from students reporting average state of hope on personal adjustment, global life satisfaction, and self-reported grade point average (Gilman et al., 2006). Hopeful thinking of an individual greatly impacts to their academic success. Students with high hope demonstrate superior academic success when compared to students with low hopefulness across elementary, junior high school, high school, and college (Cheavens et al., 2005).

Past research showed that hope is positively associated with higher cumulative GPAs, higher graduation rates, and reduced risk of dropping out, when compared with related factors (Snyder et al., 2002, as cited in Gallagher et al., 2017). Increasing the state of hope became an intervention to promote an active school performance thru increasing graduation rates and reducing dropouts. From Bryce et al (2021), students with high hope had increased, whereas students with low hope had decreased, odds of retention. Hope emphasizes goal pursuit, focusing on one's motivation to pursue goals and ability to identify tenable routes for goal achievement.

The study of Day et al., (2010) and Gallagher et al., (2017) shed light on the power of individuals' internal factors. The findings indicate that student's thoughts and beliefs about the future informs academic achievement and life outlooks above and beyond the traditional predictors of academic achievement.

Students with high hope have been shown to be highly effective in performing well in educational contexts. Hopeful students are more likely to engage in meaningful school activities; they, in turn, are more likely to achieve better academic performance (Amundson et al., 2013). Scores on hope measurement have been found to be predictive of academic achievement across all grade levels (Sung et al., 2011). Hope scores foresee achievement outcomes across multiple student levels. The agency aspect of hope can describe both skills and outcomes.

Scores on hope measurement significantly predicted elementary students' achievement test scores as well as higher scores on the Iowa Test of Basic Skills even when locus of control and self-worth were controlled for (Snyder et al., 1997, as cited in Seir up and Rose, 2011). The higher scores on trait hope facets, agency and pathways, for students in their first year of undergraduate study both shared a significant positive relationship with final degree mark at the end of 3 years of study (Day et al., 2010).

Hope and optimism are linked with be students who exhibit heightened feelings of hope are more likely to prepare to achieve academically by studying and participating in extracurricular activities. Chang (1998) found that college students who report high levels of hope tend to exhibit greater problem-solving skills and are more likely to actively address their problems than those reporting low levels of hope. High-hope college students are also more likely to graduate college and less likely to be suspended from school because of poor academic performance (Snyder et al., 2002). Higher hope consistently is related to better outcomes in academics, athletics, physical health, psychological adjustment, and psychotherapy (Snyder, 2002).

Hope was the only factor that had unique effects when examining predictors and controlling for academic history. The relation between hope and educational outcomes is becoming increasingly clear. Although many constructs may be associated with academic outcomes, the results suggest that hope may be one of the most important factors when examining unique contributions and controlling for educational history. Identifying students who would benefit from hope promoting interventions may therefore provide an important avenue for educators to promote improved academic retention and performance (Gallagher et al., 2017).

Self-esteem and Academic Success

Acquiring knowledge can be influenced by many aspects of the learner's psychological characteristics, such as self-esteem. According to Rosenberg (1965), self-esteem is one's positive or negative attitude toward oneself and one's evaluation of one's own thoughts and feelings overall in relation to oneself. Self-esteem is regarded as a personal psychological characteristic relating to self-judgment based on one's values about humans (Alesi et al., 2012).

The purpose of self-esteem is to feel and imagine that people nurtured in their mind over time about their self. Having a strong will and self-confidence, decision-making power and originality, creativity, sanity and mental health is directly related to self-esteem and sense of self-worth. It also refers to an individual's sense of his or her value or worth, or the extent to which a person values, approves of, appreciates, prizes, or likes him or herself. Research on the students' self-esteem correlate with academic success. A total sample of 600 respondents was selected randomly from various departments at the University of Swat. The researchers of the past study utilized the Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale (RSES), and the students were also asked about their academic success from their previous semesters. Results manifested a significant positive correlation between students' GPAs and their scores on the self-esteem scale. It was concluded from the results that students with higher self-esteem level had a higher academic outcome (Correlating, 2018, as cited in Tus, 2020).

As mentioned by Zhao et al. (2021) in their studies, adolescent self-esteem positively predicts academic engagement. High levels of self-esteem can increase the academic engagement of adolescents. The findings on the study of Subon (2020), about relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement support past studies. Individuals with high levels of self-esteem set stricter standards and only consider themselves "good enough" when they met those standards, resulting in positive self-evaluation and increasing academic engagement (Filippello et al., 2019). Tohid et al. (2014) indicate on their study that there is very high correlation between academic achievement and self-esteem and concluded that there is significant positive correlation between self-esteem and academic achievement.

The General Weighted Average (GWA), self-esteem and behavior problems of 105 male adolescents with migrant-working fathers were gathered. Results showed a significant relationship present between self-esteem and academic success. A relationship also was found between behavior problems and academic success (Lactao & de Guzman, 2011).

Kharsah's and Latada's (2016) study also ascertained the findings by previous studies that significant relationships existed between the levels of self-esteem and academic success. Students who are confident in their academic abilities will put more effort into academic tasks, while those who lack self-confidence will be less engaged in their studies and are more likely to give up (Zhao, 2021). Mohammad (2010) highlights the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement in the preuniversity students. He included that the students' level of self-esteem was a significant determinant in their academic achievement. If students develop higher levels of self-esteem, they will exhibit higher academic achievement. Muhammad's (2010) findings were supported by Rosli et al. (2011). Using 220 second-year medical students at a public university, they performed a cross-sectional study to investigate the association between self-esteem and students' academic achievement. The results showed that students with higher self-esteem performed better in their academic and they concluded that self-esteem is one of the key factors that contribute to individual's academic success.

Arshad (2015) concluded that there exists a strong positive correlation between self-esteem and academic achievement in university students. Furthermore, it can be said that high level of self-esteem leads to good academic success.

The results shows that self-esteem is an individual trait, and that high self-esteem promotes learning, therefore emphasizing that higher self-esteem will give promising results for students since self-esteem helps uplift oneself (del Mundo, 2021). Self-esteem and academic success are interrelated factors. There are studies supported the idea of the relationship between academic success of the students and their self-esteem.

Positive Outlook and Academic Success

Optimism is a cognitive construct (expectancies regarding future outcomes) that also relates to motivation: optimistic people exert effort, whereas pessimistic people disengage from effort (Carver & Scheier, 2014). Optimists have a positive outlook on future events and pessimists have more negative expectations. Optimists have a general expectancy of positive results which have been proven to have a positive relationship with success in attaining goals (Shepperd et al., 1996). Lopicillo et al., (2015) pointed out that positive outlook is an optimistic way of thinking about people, situation, events and any possibilities in life and nature. Positive thinking can be used effectively to change several bad habits especially with pessimism (Conger, 2017). This helps promote the idea of ensuring that everything is possible in the world.

Optimism, within certain ranges, has generally a positive correlation with academic achievement, and especially with its self-perception. Students who experience better academic achievement in college have more successful careers and experience better life outcomes (Rand et al., 2020). Studies investigating the relationship between optimism and academic success revealed that optimism was positively associated with students' well-being, adjustment levels, self-efficacy, social support and academic achievements (Richardson et al., 2012; Macaskill & Denovan 2013; Tetzner & Becker 2018). Çelik and Saricam (2018) indicate that there is a statistically positive correlation between the grit and the positive thinking skills. As the students' positive thinking skill scores increase, their grit scores also increase. It can be said that students who think positively have more grit or the persevering students are thinking

more positively.

Students who perceive positive expectancies in the pursuit of goals are more likely to persevere in the face of difficulty and identify more ways to reach the goals set in the event of obstacle. In the academic context, situational optimism – generally defined as having good expectations for specific situations – is linked to a higher GPA and moderates the causal relationship between ability and academic success (Noris, 2003). Highly optimistic students tend to have a higher GPA and a lower rate of course attrition (Ruthig et al., 2007). On the other hand, pessimistic students tend to perform worse academically (El-Anzi, 2005; Yates, 2002). Factors that may arise (Mcbride, 2012).

Optimism relates to positive outcomes in achievement, coping strategies, and adjustment in college (Lin & Peterson, 1990; Aspinwall & Taylor, 1992; Chang, 1996). Positive thinking skills for children and adolescents, to strengthen and improve the positive relationship with the self and positive relationships with others and life can increase their self-esteem and academic achievement and seems to be very useful (Pourrazavi & Hafezian 2017). Researchers spent a lot of time studying about optimism. It turns out that an optimistic attitude helps to be happier, more successful, and healthier.

Methodology

Research Design

This study will use a Descriptive Correlational Research Design. A descriptive correlational design primarily describes relationships among variables, without seeking to establish a causal connection. It is used in research studies that aim to provide static pictures of situations as well as establish the relationship between different variables (McBurney & White, 2009). In this method, the researcher will measure the students' state of hope, self-esteem, positive outlook, and academic success and assess the statistical relationship. It will investigate the strength and/or direction of the relationship between students' hope, self-esteem, and positive outlook to their academic success.

Respondents

The participants of this study are Grade 11 and 12 senior high school learners from different schools in Lopez West District. The target of the researcher is the senior high school students because they are preparing for their exits (higher education, entrepreneurship, employment, or middle-level skills development). After finishing senior high school, they are expected to create their new journey and become successful in their career paths. As an output, the Guidance Counselor/ Coordinators and Mental Health Coordinators create an intervention program for the senior high school students. And this intervention program will help the students to strengthen their hope, self-esteem, and positive outlook, and to improve their academic success.

Since this research aimed to be the basis of future intervention for the senior high school students, the intervention may help the students to strengthen their hope, self-esteem, and positive outlook and improve their academic success. By helping the students become hopeful, confident, and optimistic, they can easily create steps and plans to have a brighter future after they exit senior high school.

Instrument

To address objective number 1 the researcher will use a self-made questionnaire to identify the demographic profile of the students. This includes the Grade point average (GPA), Family income, and Living

Arrangement of the students.

Moreover, to address objective number 2, the respondents will make use of standardized tests such as the Hope Scale, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, and Life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R).

The Hope Scale (Snyder et al., 1991) is a 12-item measure of hope for people over 15 years. In particular, the scale is divided into two subscales that comprise Snyder's cognitive model of hope: (1) Agency (i.e., goal-directed energy) and (2) Pathways (i.e., planning to accomplish goals). Of the 12 items, 4 make up the Agency subscale and 4 make up the Pathways subscale. The remaining 4 items are fillers. Each item is answered using an 8-point Likert-type scale ranging from Definitely False to Definitely True. Hope Scale offers a brief, internally consistent, and valid self-report measure of ongoing goal-directed thinking that may be useful to researchers and applied professionals (Snyder et al., 1996). Also, scores gained in the hope scale are a meaningful predictor of educational performance at all educational grades (Shehni-Yailagh et al., 2011).

The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale is a ten-item Likert Scale with items answered on a four-point scale from strongly agree to strongly disagree. It is an instrument that is commonly used to measure self-esteem and has been used in several fields and has demonstrated comparable stability in many cultures (Ju-Young and Eun-Young, 2019).

The Revised Life Orientation Test (LOT-R) is a 10-item scale that measures how optimistic or pessimistic people feel about the future. The 10-item LOT-R comprises a combination of direct scored, reverse-scored, and filler items. The respondents indicated the extent to which they agreed with each of the items on a 5-point scale from 0 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree). These items are designed to apply to all individuals irrespective of their demographic characteristics and serve to investigate attitudes about future events that

we all consciously or unconsciously possess.

Lastly, for objective 3 the Researcher-made instrument for students' academic success was used. According to York et al (2015), academic success includes academic achievement, attainment of learning objectives, acquisition of desired skills and competencies, satisfaction, persistence, and career success. The researcher developed an instrument that consists of questions that will investigate the academic achievement, acquisition of desired skills and competencies, and satisfaction. This researcher-made questionnaire is composed of 25 items with each of the item has 5-point scale from 0 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree).

Procedure

To ensure a smooth turnout of the data gathering, the following procedures were considered. Before conducting the research and administering the instruments, the researcher will ask for supervision from the Registered Guidance Counselor or Psychometrician about the research instruments specifically the Hope Scale, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, and Life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R). The researcher also asked for the validation of the Research-made Questionnaire about factors affecting academic success and to measure academic success from the Psychometrician and Language Expert. Their expertise is needed in order to have a concrete interpretation of the results.

After the test validation, the researcher secured a written permit to conduct a study from the District Supervisor of the Lopez West District.

Before conducting the test, the participants were fully informed about the nature and purpose of the research by sending a letter to them. They were assured about the confidentiality of their identities. Due to the quarantine status and alert level of the Quezon Province, the researcher will secure the safety of the students by isolating and disinfecting the test instruments. The instruments will be delivered to the students during the distribution of the modules.

The first part of the researcher instrument is the Learner's Profile followed by Hope Scale, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, Life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R), and the Research-Made Questionnaire about Academic success.

The instruments were collected on the retrieval day of the students' modules. The researcher asked for guidance from the Psychometrician/ Guidance Counselor for the interpretation of the learner's Hope Scale, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, Life Orientation Test-Revised (LOT-R), and Research-made Questionnaire about academic success. After the interpretation, the Statistician assisted the researcher in analyzing and interpreting the data.

Ethical Considerations

Respect the Person

In this study, the researchers assured that the participants were informed about the process and aspects of the research. The participants are knowledgeable about their safety, as well as the confidentiality, obligation, and responsibilities of both (the researchers and participants). Also, an agreement between the participants and researcher in this study was being settled that whenever they choose not to join or decided not to participate in the study, they can freely withdraw.

Results and Discussion

Part I. The Mental Health Perspective of the Respondents

Table 1. *Students' State of Hope*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1. I energetically pursue my goals.	6.84	1.425	Mostly True	1
2. My past experiences have prepared me well for my future.	6.69	1.541	Mostly True	2
3. I can think of many ways to get the things in life that are important to me.	6.67	1.438	Mostly True	3
4. There are lots of ways around any problem.	6.50	1.482	Mostly True	4
5. Even when others get discouraged, I know I can find a way to solve the problem.	6.46	1.398	Mostly True	5
6. I meet the goals that I set for myself.	6.04	1.707	Mostly True	6
7. I can think of many ways to get out of a jam.	5.73	1.486	Somewhat True	7
8. I've been pretty successful in life.	5.65	1.878	Somewhat True	8
Average	6.32	0.943	Mostly True	

Hope is the process of thinking about one's goals, along with the motivation to move toward those goals (agency), and the ways to achieve those goals (pathways) (Snyder,1995). Table 4 shows the computed weighted mean of the respondents' Self- Assessed Mental Health Perspective in terms of their State of Hope. From the table, respondents assessed that mostly true (WAM=6.84) to them they energetically pursue their goals. Also, it is mostly true (WAM=6.69) to them that their past experiences have prepared them well for

their future. Along with this, it is mostly true (WAM=6.67) to the respondents that they can think of many ways to get the things in life that are important to them. In addition, it is mostly true (WAM=6.50) to them that there are lots of ways to solve any problem.

Moreover, it is mostly true (WAM=6.46) to the respondents that even when others get discouraged, they can find a way to solve the problem. It is also mostly true (WAM=6.04) to them that they can meet the goals that they set for themselves.

Furthermore, it is somewhat true (WAM=5.73) that the respondents can think of many ways to get out of a jam. Lastly, it is somewhat true (WAM=5.65) to them that they have been pretty successful in life. Generally, the respondents' perspective about their hope is mostly true (WAM=6.32).

Table 2. *Students' State of Self-Esteem*

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I wish I could have more respect for myself.	2.33	0.697	Disagree	1
2. I take a positive attitude toward myself.	2.32	0.652	Disagree	2
3. On the whole, I am satisfied with myself.	2.18	0.624	Disagree	3
4. I am able to do things as well as most other people.	2.12	0.549	Disagree	4
5. I feel that I'm a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others.	2.08	0.558	Disagree	5
6. I feel that I have a number of good qualities.	2.04	0.544	Disagree	6
7. At times I think I am no good at all.	1.95	0.768	Disagree	7
8. I certainly feel useless at times.	1.73	0.740	Strongly Disagree	8
9. I feel I do not have much to be proud of.	1.56	0.768	Strongly Disagree	9
10. All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure.	1.50	0.818	Strongly Disagree	10
Average	1.98	0.311	Disagree	

Self-esteem is an overall assessment of the individual's worthiness, expressed in a positive or negative orientation towards them (Minev, 2018). Table 5 reveals the computed weighted mean of the assessed mental health perspective in terms of self-esteem. The table showed that the respondents disagreed (WAM=2.33) with the statement "I wish I could have more respect for myself". In line with this, the respondents disagreed (WAM=2.32) that they take positive attitude toward themselves. The respondents also disagreed (WAM=2.18) that they are satisfied with themselves.

They disagreed (WAM= 2.12) that they are able to do things as well as most other people. In addition, respondents disagree (WAM=2.08) that they are the person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others. Moreover, the respondents disagree (WAM=2.04) that they have a number of good qualities. Furthermore, the respondents disagree (WAM=1.95) that at times they think that they are no good at all. They strongly disagree (WAM=1.73) that feel useless at times. The respondents strongly disagree (WAM=1.26) that they have much to be proud of. Lastly, the respondents strongly disagree (WAM=1.50) that All in all, they are inclined to feel that they are failure.

Table 3. *Students' State of Positive Outlook*

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Overall, I expect more good things to happen to me than bad.	3.36	0.709	Strongly Agree	1
2. I'm always optimistic about my future.	3.19	0.654	Agree	2
3. In uncertain times, I usually expect the best.	3.11	0.692	Agree	3
4. If something can go wrong for me, it will.	2.36	0.674	Disagree	4
5. I hardly ever expect things to go my way.	2.19	0.687	Disagree	5
6. I rarely count on good things happening to me.	2.10	0.704	Disagree	6
Average	2.72	0.334	Agree	

According to Carver and Scheier (2014), optimism is a cognitive construct (expectancies regarding future outcomes) that also relates to motivation: optimistic people exert effort, whereas pessimistic people disengage from effort. Optimists have a positive outlook on future events and pessimists have more negative expectations.

Table 3 showed the computed weighted mean of the respondents' Self-Assessed Mental Health Perspective in terms of Life Orientation. From the table, respondents assessed that they strongly agree (WAM=3.36) that they expect more good things to happen to them than bad. Along with this, they agree (WAM=3.19) that they are always optimistic about their future. In addition, the respondents agree (WAM=3.11) that they unusually expect the best in uncertain times.

Moreover, the respondents disagree (WAM=2.36) that if something can go wrong for them, it will. Furthermore, they disagree (WAM=2.19) that they hardly expect things to go on their way. Lastly, the respondents disagree (WAM=2.10) that they rarely count good things happening to them. Generally, the respondents agree (WAM=2.72) that they have a positive orientation in life.

Part II. Students' Perception of their Academic Success

Table 4. *Students' Perception of their Academic Success*

Statement	Mean (Std. Dev.)	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Satisfaction	4.05	0.589	Agree	1
Acquisition of Desired Skills and Competencies	3.93	0.529	Agree	2
General Average	3.99	0.496	Agree	

Table 4 showed the students' overall perception in their academic success. It revealed that the respondents agree (WAM=4.05) that they are satisfied in their academic. In addition, the respondents agree (WAM=3.93) that they acquired the desired skills and competencies. Generally, the respondents agree (WAM=3.99) that they acquired the desired skills and competencies and satisfied in their academic success.

Part III. The Significant Relationship between the students' mental health perspective, and their academic success and academic achievement

Table 5. *Significant Relationship in Students' Mental Health Perspective of Hope and their Perceived Academic Success and Academic Achievement*

Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of Relationship	p- value	Conclusion
Acquisition of Desired Skills and Competencies	0.349**	Moderately Weak Positive Relationship	0.000	Significantly Correlated
Academic Satisfaction	0.213**	Weak Positive Relationship	0.000	Significantly Correlated
Academic Performance	0.092	Weak Positive Relationship	0.091	Not Significantly Correlated

Table 5 presents the significant relationship in students' mental health perspective of hope and their perceived academic success and academic performance using Pearson R Correlation. The degree of relationship can be referred in Appendix I. Specifically, the null hypothesis herein assumes that the students' mental health perspective of hope is not significantly correlated with their perceived academic success and academic performance.

On the other hand, the alternative hypothesis states that there is a significant correlation. Using the p-value method, the null hypothesis is rejected whenever the p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance; otherwise, Ho fails to be rejected.

As shown, the students' mental health perspective of hope has a moderately weak positive relationship with their acquisition of desired skills and competencies while the former has a weak positive relationship with the students' academic satisfaction and academic performance. Further, since students' mental health perspective of hope has a p-value of less than 0.05 when related to students' acquisition of desired skills and competencies, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, and therefore conclude that at 5% level of significance, significant relationship was established.

Table 6. *Significant Relationship in Students' Mental Health Perspective of Self-Esteem and their Perceived Academic Success and Academic Achievement*

Dimension	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of Relationship	p- value	Conclusion
Acquisition of Desired Skills and Competencies	0.091	Weak Positive Relationship	0.096	Not Significantly Correlated
Academic Satisfaction	0.065	Weak Positive Relationship	0.230	Not Significantly Correlated
Academic Performance	-0.046	Weak Negative Relationship	0.396	Not Significantly Correlated

Table 6 presents the significant relationship in students' mental health perspective of self-esteem and their perceived academic success and academic performance using Pearson R Correlation. The degree of relationship can be referred in Appendix I. Specifically, the null hypothesis herein assumes that the students' mental health perspective of self-esteem is not significantly correlated with their perceived academic success and academic performance.

On the other hand, the alternative hypothesis states that there is a significant correlation. Using the p-value method, the null hypothesis is rejected whenever the p-value is less than or equal to the level of significance; otherwise, Ho fails to be rejected.

As shown, the students' mental health perspective of self-esteem has a weak positive relationship with their acquisition of desired skills and competencies, and academic satisfaction while the former has a weak negative relationship with the students' academic performance.

Further, since students' mental health perspective of self-esteem has a p-value of not less than 0.05 when related to students' acquisition of desired skills and competencies, academic satisfaction, and academic performance, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, and therefore conclude that at 5% level of significance, no significant relationship was established among these variables.

Table 7. *Significant Relationship in Students' Mental Health Perspective of Life Orientation and their Perceived Academic Success and Academic Achievement*

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>Degree of Relationship</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Conclusion</i>
Acquisition of Desired Skills and Competencies	0.115*	Weak Positive Relationship	0.034	Significantly Correlated
Satisfaction	-0.070	Weak Negative Relationship	0.200	Not Significantly Correlated
Academic Performance	0.005	Weak Positive Relationship	0.929	Not Significantly Correlated

Table 7 presents the significant relationship in students' mental health perspective of life orientation and their perceived academic success and academic performance using Pearson R Correlation.

As shown, the students' mental health perspective of life orientation has a weak positive relationship with their acquisition of desired skills and competencies, and academic performance while the former has a weak negative relationship with the students' academic satisfaction. Further, since students' mental health perspective of life orientation has a p-value of less than 0.05 when related to students' acquisition of desired skills and competencies, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, and therefore conclude that at 5% level of significance, significant relationship was established.

The students' state of hope indicates that the respondents are hopeful. The respondents' hope could predict their academic success. There were researchers who have found out that hope has a great contribution to an individual's personal achievement.

According to Sierup and Rose (2011), hopeful students are more likely to engage in self-regulatory behaviors and internalizing strategies to obtain their goals of academic success. Higher hope has also been related to higher overall grade-point averages in high school (Snyder et al., 1991).

In relation to the self-esteem of students, the respondents disagreed with the indicators. The respondents disagreed with the indicator that they take a positive attitude toward themselves. From that statement, it is clearly shown that the respondents have difficulties with how they value themselves. Since the respondents belong to adolescence stage and adolescence stage is a crucial stage of development, their age might affect the perceived self-esteem. Individuals who are in their adolescent age are very sensitive and any negative criticism will reduce their self-esteem (Smith, 2011). The environment surrounding adolescent people is a highly influential factor on self-esteem. Parents and older family members need to know the specifics of adolescence and seek to help the child overcome their difficulties, treating the future full citizen with love, respect and trust (Adler, 1996 as cited in Minev, 2018). From the result of the assessed self-esteem, the respondents disagreed that they were able to do things as well as most other people. From this, it highlighted that the respondents are not confident about their abilities. According to the Psychosocial Development of Erik Erikson, during adolescence stage the adolescent will re-examine his identity and try to find out exactly who he or she is (McLeod, 2018). Furthermore, high educational stress and physical and emotional abuse by parents or other adults in the household were major risk factors correlated to low self-esteem. In the study of Maselink et al. (2017), it showed that self-esteem in early adolescence predicted depressive symptoms in late adolescence as well as early adulthood.

The students' state of positive outlook described that the respondents are optimistic and have a positive outlook. Optimists have a general expectancy of positive results which have been proven to have a positive relationship with success in attaining goals (Shepperd et al., 1996). In the academic context, situational optimism – generally defined as having good expectations for specific situations – is linked to a higher GPA and moderates the causal relationship between ability and academic success (Noris, 2003). Highly optimistic students tend to have a higher GPA and a lower rate of course attrition (Ruthig et al., 2007). Optimism relates to positive outcomes in achievement, coping strategies, and adjustment in college (Lin & Peterson, 1990; Aspinwall & Taylor, 1992; Chang, 1996).

Researchers spent a lot of time studying about optimism. It turns out that an optimistic attitude helps to be happier, more successful, and healthier.

Regarding the association between students' academic achievement and their state of hope, the result implies that the state of hope of the students affects their academic success. Past research showed that hope is positively associated with higher cumulative GPAs, higher graduation rates, and reduced risk of dropping out, when compared with related factors (Snyder et al., 2002, as cited in Gallagher et al., 2017). Bryce et al. (2021), students with high hope had increased, whereas students with low hope had decreased, odds of retention. Hope emphasizes goal pursuit, focusing on one's motivation to pursue goals and ability to identify tenable routes for goal achievement.

By increasing the state of hope of the students, it will promote an active performance in academe. Hopeful students are more likely to engage in meaningful school activities; they, in turn, are more likely to achieve better academic performance (Amundson et al., 2013).

In relation to the correlation of self-esteem and academic success, the result refutes the findings on the study of Subon (2020) and Filippello et al., (2019), about relationship between self-esteem and academic achievements. Subon (2020) concluded that self-esteem has a significant relationship to the academic success of the students. According to Filippello et al., (2019), individuals with high levels of self-esteem set stricter standards and only consider themselves "good enough" when they met those standards, resulting in positive self-evaluation and increasing academic engagement.

In this study, the self-esteem of the students is not significantly correlated with the academic success of the students. Further study on the correlation of self-esteem and study habits on the academic performance of 86 students from the School of Engineering of Universidad Tecnológica del Perú; findings suggested that self-esteem does not significantly affect academic performance, but the study habits do affect academic performance (Chilca, 2017). In the study of Tus (2020), the academic success of the respondents is not significantly correlated to the self-esteem of the senior high school students. The student's academic performance apparently showed no bearing with the self-esteem of the student respondents. Although they showed positive perception of their self-esteem, it failed to establish possible correlation with their academic performance (Olea et al., 2012). There is no significant relationship that exists between the levels of self-esteem and academic performance (Estrella, 2015).

With regards to the correlation between the positive outlook and academic success, the result indicated that students who are optimistic and have positive outlook can affect their academic success. This was supported by Ruthig et al., (2007). He emphasized that highly optimistic students tend to have a higher GPA and a lower rate of course attrition. Students who perceive positive expectancies in the pursuit of goals are more likely to persevere in the face of difficulty and identify more ways to reach the goals set in the event of obstacle. In the academic context, situational optimism – generally defined as having good expectations for specific situations – is linked to a higher GPA and moderates the causal relationship between ability and academic success (Noris, 2003). On the other hand, pessimistic students tend to perform worse academically (El-Anzi, 2005; Yates, 2002).

In the study of Hayat et al. (2022), the result showed that students' academic optimism was positively and significantly associated with their academic achievement. The results also indicated that there was a considerable, positive correlation between student identification and their academic achievement.

By helping the students become optimistic in life, they become more committed to achieve their goals, more successful in achieving their goals, more satisfied with their lives, and have better mental and physical health when compared to more pessimistic people. This could help them to have a positive outlook in life and in academe.

Conclusions

From the gathered data, the respondents' perspective about their hope is mostly true. They are hopeful that they can achieve in their academics and be the person they wanted to be in the future. Based on the data, the respondents disagree with the indicators about their self-esteem. It indicated that the respondents have personal issues that need to be addressed. For the respondents' positive outlook, they agreed that they have a positive life orientation. They emphasized that they have a positive orientation in life.

From the evaluated relationship between students' hope and academic success, there is a significant relationship. It is supported by the study of Snyder (2002) and Bryce et al (2021) that hope of the students affects their academic success.

In terms of self-esteem and academic success, there is no significant relationship. Even though there were studies that emphasized that self-esteem has a significant relationship with the student's academic success, the result of this study refuted this. The result of this study is supported by the study of Tus (2020) and Olea et al., (2012). They concluded that the academic success of the respondents is not significantly correlated to the self-esteem of the senior high school students.

In terms of positive outlook and academic success, there is a significant relationship. The result of the study is supported by the study of Hayat et al. (2022) and Norris (2003) that the students who perceive positive expectancies in the pursuit of goals are more likely to persevere in the face of difficulty and identify more ways to reach the goals set in the event of an obstacle.

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